

B2-InF Progress Report

In the last months the B2-InF consortium has been working on STAGE 1 of the project, focusing on collecting information from society about their perspectives and knowledge on ART as well as from clinics regarding their current services and approach.

The **main challenge in the project's fieldwork has been data collection** owing to the nature of the substantial qualitative study that had to be carried out in eight different countries across Europe, including around 160 semi-structured interviews. This meant that eight different fieldwork teams were required, working in eight different contexts. To homogenize the data collection process, two handbooks were developed initially.

The **handbooks** were meant to develop 1) a **shared interview methodology** among the research groups and 2) a **training session for the interviewers**. Two training sessions were carried out in parallel, one for Western European countries (Belgium, Italy, Switzerland and Spain), led by **APLICA Coop**, and one for Eastern European countries (Albania, Macedonia, Kosovo, and Slovenia), led by **Healthgrouper**. The training mainly consisted in explaining to interviewers the **aims of the project and the objectives to be achieved through the data collection process**. In addition, the training sessions gave thorough information on how to appropriately fill out the documents to achieve consistency among the data collected.

Ten to fifteen interviews were conducted in each country in vernacular languages and subsequently translated into English. Interviewees were selected following specific criteria, according to variables previously set by the project. Selected subjects were 18 to 30 years of age, including men, women and other genders. Much effort has been put to obtain a sample in each country, including people of different sexual orientations, religions and levels of education. However, this was not always possible, as, in each country, the laws and culture dictate the sample. Each research team was in charge of selecting the sample in their context, leveraging on their networks. This means that **the sample was not randomized, but was an intentional sample** (something common and applicable in qualitative research) **aiming to capture different discourses around the topic and different mindsets**.

With the interview data collection completed, B2-InF is now moving on to its thematic analysis. The consortium is very pleased with the results so far, with much appreciation for the hard work of APLICA and its significant efforts in conducting such complex coordination in close collaboration with Healthgrouper.

Fertility Europe & B2-InF: A powerful synergy.

Anita Fincham
Manager at Fertility Europe.

Fertility Europe is the umbrella association for infertility patients, which includes solely patient representatives: *“We are all pretty much people with the experience of infertility”*, - says **Anita Fincham**, manager at Fertility Europe. This means that just as most patient associations, it is **mainly run by volunteers who are fueled by passion and firm intention** but often lack the know-how when it comes to running such an organization. This has turned into a strength pushing them to help each other so that **for each new member, it gets easier and easier to be more efficient and carry out activities properly**: *“The new volunteers no longer have to waste time trying to reinvent the wheel”*.

They are **primarily interested in supporting and promoting the best access to fertility treatment in Europe**. However, at the same time, they would like to address the other side of the spectrum, such as **introducing fertility education in schools and everyday life to prevent young people from encountering related issues later in their lives**. Fertility Europe also works to educate medical staff on how to convey information about fertility and reproductive health to patients at different stages of life to make sure those wrong assumptions are not made. Everyone must have the best chances to become parents if it is something they wish for.

Many countries with meagre birth rates still do not adequately address the problem for various reasons. One of which is that the intricate web of meanings associated with fertility makes communication about the topic very complex for governments. *“There are many traps to this communication”*, - explains Anita Fincham, as history shows that governments who try communicating about fertility are often associated with traditionalist, anti-feminist parties by the general public. **The responsibility to disseminate information, educate the young and help those who are already facing problems falls upon other organizations such as B2-InF and Fertility Europe**. *“Going back to an old-school mindset of family planning is never our intention. We just want to arm the young with the knowledge and tools to make their own choices fully aware of their limitations”*.

Therefore, it is clear that the goals and purpose of Fertility Europe and B2-InF are aligned and fundamentally **intertwined in their pursuit of an improved and standardized fertility journey**. Dr. Güell, the B2-inF’s coordinator, is worried about the ambiguous information that ART services are giving to the population about infertility. *“The needs of the patients are not always put first as they should be”*, he said. In this sense, the young population needs to be better informed about fertility, and understand their own body: *“To study the causes of infertility and trying to restore fertility must be the first steps, both from a health and economic point of view”*, concludes Dr. Güell.

Fertility Europe was pleased to join this project and fully supports collecting accurate data among young adults. This specific group of people is crucial in the fight against infertility, who are also still in time to make real-life changes. Mrs. Fincham highlights how important it is for all organizations and institutions specialized in the field to support each other, creating consistent **synergies that will open conversations at the European level leading to real change**.

All in all, B2-InF and Fertility Europe are there where policymakers fail.

The Importance of Fertility Awareness

Fertility awareness is overlooked across Europe, with very few countries providing fundamental knowledge in schools to youngsters, including Denmark and the UK. One of the many factors explaining this is governments' pressure to cater to the opposite problem: contraception. Unfortunately, what is ignored is that contraception and fertility are part of the same issue, two sides of the same coin. Teaching the young about fertility and taking care of factors influencing their reproductive health helps them make the right choices.

"We would like to arm the young with the knowledge to make the right choices at the right time";- Says Anita Fincham on behalf of Fertility Europe. "Being better informed about fertility will empower the population in order to make their decisions not just healthier for themselves, but also their future children", says Dr Güell. Fertility must not be taken for granted, as macroscopic data reveals: 1 out of 10 couples has infertility at the moment, and birth rates have significantly decreased in the western world. In fact, in 2019, the total fertility rate in the EU was 1.53 live births per woman, according to EUROSTAT.

Family planning dynamics have changed over time, as more opportunities for self-fulfilment in one's life are available, which has led to a different timeline for any individual to decide to have children. In addition, the conception of the family itself has changed. All these are positive changes that must be supported, but the freedom of any given individual to have children of their own must be guaranteed.

Knowledge is power.

31st National IVF Conference

Brno, Czech Republic

One of the most important events in Central Europe about Infertility and IVF was November 9-10 at the **31st Congress of Assisted Reproduction** in Brno, the Czech Republic. Joining the exclusive list of professionals in the field of ART, including the Society of Assisted Reproduction of the Czech Republic and Slovakia, are Medistella co-founders Anna Dostalova and Michaela Novotna. These highly established ladies were honored to represent their collaboration in the very distinct research project, B2-InF, at this 2-day event.

The B2-InF project helps to align the public's perceptions of ART with that of the government in hopes of exacting change to bring better services, support, and awareness of Assisted Reproduction. This project fits in line with the events discussions surrounding ART including different medicines, approaches and evolving technologies, presenting of the data available from our National Register of ART, plus news and updates from ESHRE. Medistella's presence was welcomed as they answered questions about B2-InF project objectives as their expertise and experience in ART make them acutely aware of all sides and they are able to provide valuable detail.

At the event, the highly respected and specialized audience of leaders in the field agreed that the B2InF project is extremely important and that the results will have a great impactful to the future of ART. In addition to deep and interesting discussions about the project goals, Medistella was able to address the motivation of donors, the unique perspectives between genders and sociocultural views, and ways to prevent issues with fertility. Anna and Michaela were also proud to bring attention to the specialized communities of Czech and Slovakia, their hometowns.

The poster is available for download in [Zenodo](#).

What's next

The first stage of the project, focusing on collecting information from society about their perspectives and knowledge on ART as well as from clinics regarding their current services and approach, is coming to an end, opening the path for the second stage:

Three main objectives compose the second stage:

1. To compare views of the general public with the information provided by clinics;
2. To assess their alignment from gender, socio-cultural, and legal perspectives;
3. To produce national guidelines that identify concrete research goals needed to make ART better aligned with society's needs, expectations, and values.

B2-InF's gender content analysis will specifically focus on gender differences concerning values and opinions related to different decision capacities and opinions regarding gender differences in the responsibility of ART clinics and ART users.

During the second stage, the project will try to go beyond the fundamental male/female dichotomy and also investigate, where possible, representations of and information about transgender and intersex populations, as they are becoming increasingly involved with ART technologies.

In addition to the above, this stage will also compare the results of stage one concerning socio-cultural analysis, focusing on the following activities:

- To observe how young people approach ART (Is it a scientific advance or a sociological threat? The socio-cultural references and values mobilized to justify their representations?).
- To evaluate the sociodemographic and socio-cultural characteristics that impact ART knowledge, awareness, and representations. (Do family situations, religion, economic status, education level, or origins play a role in how ART is known, perceived and judged?)
- To identify expectations regarding ART among young nationals that conform to or diverge from dominant representations (statistically speaking, or the most accepted/tolerated) in each selected country.

B2-InF legal analysis is interested in analyzing Social Perceptions of ART and its relationship to ART's legal and case law regulations, including soft law, at national, EU and third-country levels. B2-InF will also do a legal revision of the Information about ART.

The second stage of the project will last sixteen months.